

**ҚИШЛОҚ ХЎЖАЛИГИ ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИШИДА ТЕХНИКА
ВОСИТАЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС
ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ**

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2 son kasb hunar maktabi

traktor va qishloq xo'jalik agregatlari fani o'qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada traktor va uni qishloq xo'jaligidagi ahamiyati haqida gapirish bilan birga, zamonaviy mashinalar, texnika vositalari, asbob-uskunalar va boshqa ishlab chiqarish vositalari qishloq xo'jaligini intensiv rivojlantirishda muhimligi ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Traktor, qishloq, texnika, hosil, natija, tartib.

Аннотация: Помимо разговора о тракторе и его значении в сельском хозяйстве, в статье подчеркивается значение современных машин, технических средств, оборудования и других средств производства в интенсивном развитии сельского хозяйства.

Ключевые слова: Трактор, село, техника, урожайность, результат, порядок действий.

Abstract: In addition to talking about the tractor and its importance in agriculture, the article emphasizes the importance of modern machines, technical means, equipment and other means of production in the intensive development of agriculture.

Key words: Tractor, village, equipment, productivity, result, procedure.

Qishloq xo'jaligini intensiv rivojlantirishda yuqori unumli zamonaviy mashinalar, texnika vositalari, asbob-uskunalar va boshqa ishlab chiqarish

vositalarining ahamiyati beqiyosdir. Tarmoqni barqaror sur'atlar bilan rivojlantirish uchun uning texnika bazasini yuksaltirishga jiddiy e'tibor qaratish lozim. Qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishida texnika vositalaridan foydalanishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari quyidagilar:

- qishloq xo'jaligida texnika vositalaridan foydalanish mavsumiy xarakterga egaligi ulardan foydalanish samaradorligini oshirish bilan bog'liq muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi (ayniqsa o'rim-yig'im kombaynlari, seyalkalar va shu kabi boshqa texnika-mashinalarda). Chunki qimmat turadigan yuqori unumli texnikalar qisqa vaqt davomida foydalanilib, yilning ko'p qismida bekor turib qoladi, bu esa ulardan optimal foydalanish va iqtisodiy samaradorlikka salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi;

- ochiq sharoitda ish olib borishda moddiy-buyumlashgan ko'rinishdagi texnika resurslari tabiiy-iqlim sharoitlari ta'siriga ko'proq uchraydi va ularni saqlash bo'yicha qo'shimcha sarf-xarajatlar qilinishini talab etadi.

Xozirgi kunda qishloq xo'jaligining moddiytexnika ta'minotida quyidagi ayrim muammolar mavjud:

- paxta va g'alladan tashqari boshqa qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari yetishtirishga ixtisoslashgan xo'jaliklarning mexanizasiyalashganlik darajasi yuqori darajada emas (masalan, bog'dorchilik va sabzavotchilikda 35- 40 % atrofida);

- dehqon xo'jaliklari qishloq xo'jaligi yalpi mahsulotining uchdan ikki qismidan ko'prog'ini berayotgan bo'lishiga qaramay, ularda asosiy ishlab chiqarish jarayonlari qo'l kuchi bilan bajariladi va mexanizasiya vositalari bilan qurollanish darajasi juda past darajada, ularni minitraktorlar, qishloq xo'jaligi mashinalari, yoqilg'i, mineral o'g'itlar va o'simliklarni himoyalash vositalari, omixta yem, paxta shroti va sheluxa kabi ko'pchilik moddiy resurslar bilan ta'minlash tizimli yo'lga qo'yilmagan;

- chorvachilikka ixtisoslashgan ko'pchilik xo'jaliklarda chorva mollarini saqlash va parvarishlash uchun maxsus binolar, avtomatlashtirilgan oziqlantirish liniyalari, konsentrat ozuqa tayyorlaydigan minisexlar, tayyor mahsulotlar va moddiy

resurslarni saqlash uchun maxsus omborlar, texnika vositalarini saqlaydigan yopiq saroylar, omixta yem-xashak, kunjara va chigit sheluxasi kabi aylanma vositalar yetishmaydi.

Istiqbolda qishloq xo'jaligida ish jarayonlarining mexanizasiyalashuv darajasi ortib borishi bilan haydov va chopiq traktorlariga, chizel, plug va borona kabi mashinalar tizimiga, hosilni o'rib-yig'ib olish kombaynlariga hamda yuk tashish transporti vositalariga talab ortib boraveradi. Keyingi yillarda mamlakatimizda qishloq xo'jaligini yuqori unumli mashinalar va texnika vositalari bilan ta'minlash borasida bir qator davlat dasturlari qabul qilingan va ularni hayotga tatbiq etish bo'yicha yirik choratadbirlar amalga oshirilgan bo'lishiga qaramay, qishloq xo'jaligining ularga bo'lgan talabi to'liq qondirilgan deb bo'lmaydi. Keyingi yillarda qishloq xo'jaligida foydalanib kelinayotgan haydov va chopiq traktorlari hamda qishloq xo'jaligi mashinalarining katta qismi eskirib, o'z xizmat muddatini o'tab bo'lgani sir emas. Bu masalaga muhtaram Prezidentimiz o'z e'tiborlarini qaratib: “CHopiq traktorlarining 55 foizdan ortig'i va er haydaydigan traktorlarning 46 foizi 15 yildan ortiq vaqt mobaynida ishlatilayotgani, boshqacha aytganda, ular belgilangan foydalanish muddatini allaqachon o'tab bo'lgani, quvvati, ish unumi va yoqilg'i iste'mol qilish bo'yicha zamonaviy standartlarga javob bermaydigan eski texnikalar ekani tashvish uyg'otmasdan qolmaydi” ,- deb ta'kidlaganlar.

SHundan kelib chiqib, mamlakatimiz qishloq xo'jaligini modernizasiyalash, jumladan tarmoqning texnika parkini kengaytirish, uni yuqori unumli va resurs tejoychi zamonaviy texnika-texnologiyalar bilan qurollantirish masalasi hal qilinishi lozim bo'lgan eng ustuvor vazifalardan biri sifatida kun tartibiga qo'yildi.

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